

Bridging Adversarial and Information-Theoretic Fairness via Robustness

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Abstract—This work investigates the connection between information-theoretic and adversarial approaches to fairness in neural network classifiers. We study the theoretical robustness of these approaches to distribution shifts, which we find serves as a proxy for the generalization of fairness measures from finite training samples to the underlying population. We focus on the Equalized Odds (EO) notion of fairness, which requires the classifier output Z to be independent of sensitive attributes U given the true label Y . While Mutual Information (MI) based fairness provides an absolute measure of independence, adversarial (discriminator-based) approaches offer a computationally bounded alternative. We first bridge these paradigms by proving the existence of an optimal architecture-dependent discriminator that is both necessary and sufficient to ensure a Difference in Equalized Odds (DEO) of zero. However, we demonstrate that this adversarial fairness is inherently fragile under distributional shifts. In contrast, we find that the MI-based approach is “over-robust”; we prove that if $I(Z; U|Y) = 0$ on a source distribution, zero DEO is preserved for any target distribution sharing the same support. While this highlights robustness, it addresses shifts far more radical than those typically encountered in practice. Lastly, via experiments on benchmark fairness datasets, we show that the practical optimal discriminator complexity is often higher than theoretically predicted, gravitating toward MI-based solutions. Our results imply that treating discriminator complexity as a tunable hyperparameter can significantly optimize the fairness-accuracy curve, capturing the necessary robustness without the practical overhead of MI-based extremes.

Index Terms—Adversarial Fairness, Mutual Information, Distribution-Shift, Equalized Odds

I. INTRODUCTION

As machine learning models increasingly automate critical decision-making in domains such as finance [1], education [2], and recruitment [3], the demand for algorithmic fairness has shifted from an ethical desideratum to a regulatory requirement [4]. Among the various quantitative definitions of fairness, Group Fairness, which ensures that demographic groups are not systematically disadvantaged, has gained significant prominence. In particular, the notion of **Equalized Odds (EO)** [5] is widely adopted, as it requires the classifier’s predictions to be independent of sensitive attributes U conditional on the true label Y .

In the current landscape of fair representation learning, two primary paradigms exist for achieving EO. The first is **Information-Theoretic**, which seeks to minimize the conditional Mutual Information (MI), $I(Z; U|Y)$, between the classifier’s features Z and the sensitive attributes U . While

MI provides an absolute measure of independence, it is notoriously difficult to estimate in high dimensions and assumes an adversary with infinite computational power to extract information. The second is **Adversarial (Discriminator-based)**, where a separate neural network (the discriminator) attempts to predict U from Z , and the classifier is penalized based on the discriminator’s accuracy. This approach is more practical and reflects the computational boundedness of real-world adversaries, yet it lacks the guarantees associated with MI.

Here, we first formalize the role of discriminator complexity in achieving Equalized Odds fairness. We ask: *What level of discriminator complexity is sufficient to guarantee zero DEO, and how do these guarantees generalize beyond training?*

A central challenge in this analysis is that a classifier is trained on an empirical distribution P' , yet fairness must hold on the true population P . We bridge this gap by treating the empirical sampling process as a distributional shift within a Wasserstein-1 ball. Using recent Wasserstein distance based concentration results for empirical distribution measures [6], we demonstrate that the finite-sample error bounds can be related to the distribution-shift robustness. This allows us to analyze fairness measures via the lens of shift-robustness.

We find that while an optimal discriminator exists for any architecture, it can be fragile to distribution shifts. In contrast, MI-based fairness guarantees robustness to any shifts within the distribution support, ensuring zero DEO for any such distribution shift. We argue that while this represents a form of *over-robustness*, protecting against radical shifts rarely seen in nature, it provides the necessary stability that adversarial methods lack. Our work implies that the path to practical fairness lies in calibrating discriminator complexity toward MI-like behavior to survive the shift induced by finite-sample estimation.

Contributions. Our primary contributions are as follows:

- 1) **Generalization-as-Robustness:** We provide a rigorous link between generalization error and distributional shift using the Wasserstein-1 metric. This justifies the use of shift-robustness theory to analyze fairness generalization.
- 2) **Robustness of Adversarial Fairness:** We prove that in adversarial fairness, an EO-optimal discriminator exists that is both necessary and sufficient for ensuring zero DEO. However, we find that equalized odds breaks down with the optimal discriminator in the face of distribution shifts.

*Equal Contribution

- 3) **Robustness of MI-based Fairness:** We prove that MI-based fairness ($I(Z; U|Y) = 0$) yields equalized odds for any distribution shift within its support. We characterize this as an over-robust property which can be relaxed for real datasets.
- 4) **Empirical Complexity Tuning:** Through experiments on benchmark datasets, we show that the best-performing discriminator often has higher complexity than the EO-optimal discriminator for a static distribution, highlighting that in practice the correct discriminator choice can yield significant benefits. Our approach uses the validation set to find the best discriminator complexity.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Equalized Odds Fairness

In this section, we present the standard framework for achieving and evaluating Equalized Odds (EO) fairness. This dual-scenario approach is common in the literature for distinguishing between the information used by the learner during training and the residual information available to a potential external observer.

The following methodology centers on the Equalized Odds (EO) notion of fairness. In many real-world settings, the sensitive attribute U is statistically related to the target label Y . In these cases, EO is often preferred over Demographic Parity (DP), as the latter can be overly restrictive, forcing the classifier to ignore legitimate predictive signals and potentially leading to significant loss in utility.

1. Fair Classification (Adversarial Training Framework)

A widely adopted approach to inducing fairness is through adversarial regularization. In this scenario, a classifier is optimized to satisfy EO by competing against a label-conditioned discriminator. The standard elements are:

- **Classifier (F):** A model that maps inputs to predictions \hat{Y} . It consists of a feature extractor producing representations Z and a classifier head g_θ . Its primary objective is to maximize label accuracy.
- **Internal Discriminator (D):** An agent trained alongside the classifier to detect dependencies between Z and U . To specifically target the Equalized Odds criterion, the discriminator is conditioned on the label Y , typically implemented as n separate functions h_1, \dots, h_n (one for each class $y \in \{1, \dots, n\}$) that attempt to recover U from Z .

The objective is to minimize classification loss while maximizing the discriminator’s uncertainty. This results in the following min-max optimization:

$$\min_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \mathcal{L}_{CE}(Y, \hat{Y}) + \lambda \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \left[- \min_{h \in \mathcal{D}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] \right] \quad (1)$$

where λ is a regularization hyperparameter. This training objective encourages the model to find a representation Z where the specific discriminator class \mathcal{D} can no longer distinguish between sensitive groups within a given class y .

2. Fair Representation (Post-hoc Evaluation Framework)

While the internal discriminator is used to enforce fairness

during training, it does not necessarily represent the total information leakage. To evaluate the robustness of the resulting representations, a separate Representation Learning evaluation is typically performed:

- **External Adversary (A):** A post-hoc agent that attempts to extract sensitive information from the fixed representations Z . Unlike the internal discriminator, the adversary is not involved in the training process.

This evaluation determines whether the sensitive information was truly erased or if it was merely hidden from the specific architecture used during training. By varying the complexity of this external adversary, one can probe the gap between achieving fairness against a specific function class (such as the Canonical Discriminator \mathcal{D}_{EO}) and achieving the absolute robustness promised by Information-Theoretic fairness ($I(Z; U \mid Y) = 0$).

B. Viewing Generalization as Distribution Shift Robustness

To motivate our robustness analysis, we view generalization as robustness to distributional shifts. The m samples of training constitute an empirical distribution \hat{P}_m that differs from the true P by at most a small W_1 shift. Concentration bounds show that, with high probability, P lies inside a Wasserstein ball around \hat{P}_m . Thus, the generalization gap is exactly the robustness of f to all shifts within that ball. We outline the result as follows.

Proposition 1. (Generalization as Robustness to Distribution Shifts; from Theorem 2 in [6]) *Let P be a probability law on \mathbb{R}^d with $d > 2$, and let $\hat{P}_m = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \delta_{X_i}$ be the empirical law of m i.i.d. samples from P . Denote by $W_1(\cdot, \cdot)$ the 1-Wasserstein distance. Assume P has an exponential moment of order 2, i.e., there exists a $\gamma > 0$ such that $\mathcal{E}_{2,\gamma}(P) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} e^{\gamma|x|^2} P(dx) < \infty$.*

Then there exist positive constants $C, c > 0$ (depending only on $p = 1, d$, and on $2, \gamma, \mathcal{E}_{2,\gamma}(P)$) such that the following holds: for any confidence level $\delta \in (0, 1)$,

$$r_{m,\delta} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\log(C/\delta)}{cm}\right)^{1/d}, & \delta \geq C e^{-cm}, \\ \left(\frac{\log(C/\delta)}{cm}\right)^{1/2}, & \delta < C e^{-cm}, \end{cases}$$

and, with probability at least $1 - \delta$,

$$\left| \mathbb{E}_{\hat{P}_m}[f] - \mathbb{E}_P[f] \right| \leq \sup_{Q: W_1(Q, \hat{P}_m) \leq r_{m,\delta}} \left| \mathbb{E}_Q[f] - \mathbb{E}_{\hat{P}_m}[f] \right|$$

for any statistic f . Note that the positive constants C and c depend only on $p = 1$, the dimension d , and on the exponential moment parameters $(\gamma, \mathcal{E}_{2,\gamma}(P))$.

Remark 1 (Generalization as Distribution-Shift Robustness). *The proposition connects two ideas: sampling error and robustness to distribution shifts. It says that when we train on a finite sample, the empirical distribution \hat{P}_m is not exactly the true population P , but the difference can be understood as a small shift in distribution. Therefore, generalization is guaranteed precisely when our fairness measure (or any*

statistic) is stable under such shifts. In other words, if a fairness guarantee holds not only for the empirical distribution but also for all distributions within a small Wasserstein ball around it, then it will also hold for the true P . This makes robustness to distributional perturbations a proxy for fairness generalization, which is the direction we explore in this work.

This connection justifies our focus on distributional-shift robustness as the operative notion of fairness generalization. In the following sections, we evaluate robustness to controlled shifts within the support (e.g., chunk removal or symmetry breaking) to test whether fairness is a stable property of the learned representation Z or is very distribution sensitive. If fairness collapses under these controlled shifts, the W_1 noise inherent in finite sampling will almost certainly undermine fairness guarantees on held-out test data.

III. THEORETICAL ANALYSES

A. The Canonical Discriminator for Equalized Odds

In this section, we identify the specific adversarial complexity required to guarantee Equalized Odds (EO). Rather than assuming an adversary of arbitrary power, we define a *Canonical Discriminator* class that represents the minimal architecture sufficient to detect and eliminate EO-unfairness for a given classifier.

Definition 1 (Equalized Odds (EO) Fairness). We consider a classifier F that produces predicted labels $\hat{Y} \in \{0, 1\}$ from features Z . The classifier is EO-fair if its predictions are conditionally independent of the sensitive attributes U given the true label Y :

$$Pr(\hat{Y} = y \mid U = u_0, Y = y) = Pr(\hat{Y} = y \mid U = u_1, Y = y) \quad (2)$$

for all $y \in \{0, 1\}$ and sensitive groups u_0, u_1 .

Definition 2 (Canonical Discriminator). Given a classifier head g_θ that maps features Z to output logits, the Canonical Discriminator class \mathcal{D}_{EO} consists of functions $h : \mathbb{R}^{\dim(Z)} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ of the form:

$$h(Z) = a + b \cdot \sigma_H(g_\theta(Z)) \quad (3)$$

where σ_H is the hard-sigmoid operator and a, b are trainable scalars satisfying $0 \leq a, a + b \leq 1$ and $2a + b = 1$.

Theorem 1 (Necessity and Sufficiency). Let F be a classifier with features Z . F is guaranteed to satisfy the Equalized Odds criterion if and only if for every label $y \in \{0, 1\}$, the optimal discriminator in \mathcal{D}_{EO} fails to reduce the cross-entropy loss \mathcal{L} below the entropy of the sensitive attribute:

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{D}_{EO}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] = H(U \mid Y = y) \quad (4)$$

Remark 2 (Architectural Alignment and MI Relaxation). This result implies that the perfect adversary for enforcing fairness is not an infinitely complex network, but one whose architecture is explicitly aligned with the classifier’s own head. Consequently, the constraint required to achieve Equalized

Odds is significantly more relaxed than that of Mutual Information (MI). While MI requires $I(Z; U \mid Y) = 0$, implying that U cannot be extracted by any adversary regardless of complexity. Our result shows that fairness only necessitates that a computationally restricted form of information be zero. If the features Z are fair against this Canonical Discriminator \mathcal{D}_{EO} , the classifier F is mathematically guaranteed to be EO-fair, even if higher-complexity extractors could still theoretically recover U from Z .

Proposition 2 (Fragility under Distribution Shift). Consider a Canonical Discriminator \mathcal{D}_{EO} under a distribution $P(Z)$, and any shifted distribution $Q(Z)$ satisfying $TV(P, Q) = \delta > 0$ with $\text{supp}(Q) \subseteq \text{supp}(P)$. Then for every $y \in \{0, 1\}$ and for $\delta \rightarrow 0$, the optimal discriminator in \mathcal{D}_{EO} under Q satisfies

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{D}_{EO}} \mathbb{E}_Q[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] \geq H(U \mid Y = y) - \max \left\{ \frac{\delta^2}{2 \ln 2}, \left| \ln \frac{p}{1-p} \right| \frac{\delta}{2 \ln 2} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where $p = P(U = 1 \mid Y = y)$.

Remark 3. Under a TV shift of size δ , the canonical discriminator’s optimal loss drops below the entropy baseline by $\frac{1}{2 \ln 2} \delta^2$. Theorem 1 then implies that in this case EO is not guaranteed, thus indicating that the canonical discriminator’s fairness can be fragile.

B. How Robust is MI-Based Fairness?

The following results establish that Information-Theoretic fairness guarantees provide a significantly stronger guarantee of robustness to a wide range of distribution shifts, in contrast to discriminator-based guarantees discussed previously.

Proposition 3. [Robustness of Information-Theoretic Fairness] Let P be a source distribution and Z be a representation such that $I(Z; U \mid Y) = 0$. For any target distribution Q whose support is a subset of the source support ($\text{supp}(Q) \subseteq \text{supp}(P)$), the representation remains perfectly fair. Specifically, for any measurable classifier head $g : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$, the Equality of Odds is preserved:

$$P_Q(g(Z) \mid U = 0, Y = y) = P_Q(g(Z) \mid U = 1, Y = y)$$

Remark 4 (Absolute Robustness vs. Linear Fragility). This result confirms that MI-based fairness is support-invariant. Because $I(Z; U \mid Y) = 0$ implies that the feature distributions for $U = 0$ and $U = 1$ are identical point-wise across the support, no re-weighting or pruning of the data can ever create a statistical difference for a classifier head to exploit. This stands in stark contrast to discriminator-based fairness (Proposition 3), which we showed can collapse under any shift Q with a TV distance δ . While the linear discriminator is fooled by simple symmetry-breaking, MI-based fairness remains intact for any Q within the support.

Next, we outline the conditions under which non-zero MI loses the equalized odds guarantee under distribution shifts.

Theorem 2 (Fragility of Non-Zero Mutual Information).

Let Z be a representation such that $I(Z; U | Y) > 0$, and let the classifier head be a linear function. If the conditional entropy $H(U | Z, Y)$ is L -Lipschitz, then there exists a distribution Q and a classifier F with $\text{supp}(Q) \subseteq \text{supp}(P)$ such that F violates equalized odds on Q .

Remark 5 (Robustness of the Leaky Case). Proposition 5 suggests that even when MI is non-zero (and thus the representation is technically unfair), it only collapses under quite specific circumstances: there must exist a specific Q within the support, a specific classifier F , and the conditional entropy must satisfy L -Lipschitz smoothness. This implies that MI-based fairness is extremely robust, perhaps excessively so. It only fails if we aren't perfectly at zero MI or if Q moves outside the support of P .

Remark 6 (Over-Engineering for Real-World Shifts). The robustness of MI shown in Proposition 4 is a powerful theoretical property, but it may represent an overkill in practice. Recalling our earlier Wasserstein bounds, the shifts we actually encounter in finite sampling (where $W_1(P, \hat{P})$ is small) do not typically involve the adversarial support pruning required to break a moderately fair representation. If our goal is to protect against shifts between P and \hat{P} that are close in Wasserstein distance, the stringent requirement of $I(Z; U|Y) = 0$ can be relaxed. The safety margin provided by MI is far larger than the typical variance introduced by sampling noise.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

Our experiments are set in the adversarial fairness setting, with the objective of analyzing the impact of discriminator and adversary complexity and interpreting the findings in the context of our theoretical observations. Please note that further details, including proofs of the theoretical results, additional empirical details and experiments are all provided in <https://zenodo.org/records/18273416>.

A. Experimental Setup

Datasets. We evaluate on three tabular datasets: *Credit Card Default* [7], *Adult Census* [7], and *Heritage Health* [8]. Sensitive attributes are: *gender* (Credit), *gender* and *race* (Adult), and *age* (9 bins) and *gender* (Health). Further pre-processing and splits are described in the supplementary materials. All reported metrics are computed on held-out test sets.

Metrics. For each trained model we report:

- 1) **Classifier accuracy** (higher is better): test accuracy for predicting Y .
- 2) **Equalized odds difference (DEO)** (lower is better):

$$\sum_{y \in \{0,1\}} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \left| P(\hat{Y} = 1 | U = u, Y = y) - P(\hat{Y} = 1 | Y = y) \right|$$

- 3) **Adversary extraction score** (lower is better): predictive performance of an external adversary trained to recover U from Z (measured on the test set).
- 4) **Adversary AUC** (lower is better): ROC AUC of the external adversary on the test set; higher AUC indicates stronger leakage of sensitive information.

		Discriminator \mathcal{V}_D			Discriminator Z_D				
		AUC	\mathcal{V}_1	\mathcal{V}_2	\mathcal{V}_3	DEO	Z_1	Z_2	Z_3
Adversary \mathcal{V}_A	\mathcal{V}_1	0.774	0.593	0.586	Discriminator \mathcal{V}_D	\mathcal{V}_1	4.852	5.560	6.109
	\mathcal{V}_2	0.790	0.613	0.609		\mathcal{V}_2	4.173	5.290	5.917
	\mathcal{V}_3	0.806	0.625	0.609		\mathcal{V}_3	3.256	4.657	6.187

(a) AUC (disc. v/s adversary)

(b) DEO (layer vs. disc.)

Fig. 1: Impact of adversary and discriminator (disc.) complexity on adversary AUC and DEO for the Health dataset. All metrics reported on the test set.

Architectures and variants. For the experiments below we vary both the representation layer used for regularization and the complexity of the discriminator/adversary:

- **Representation layers:** Z_1 = penultimate layer, Z_2 = second penultimate layer, Z_3 = third penultimate layer.
- **Discriminator / adversary families:** \mathcal{V}_1 = 1 hidden layer, \mathcal{V}_2 = 2 hidden layers, \mathcal{V}_3 = 3 hidden layers.

B. Adversary Extraction and DEO by Layer and Complexity

Goal. On the Health dataset we perform two focused analyses: (i) measure how much sensitive information an external adversary can extract from different representation layers, across different choices of discriminator complexity and (ii) measure the classifier's DEO when regularization is applied at different layers using discriminators of varying complexity.

Protocol. For each choice of representation layer Z_i and training discriminator family \mathcal{V}_j we train the classifier with adversarial regularization (Equation (1)) on the training set. Hyperparameters (including learning rates and early stopping) are tuned on a validation split. After training:

- We train an *external* adversary (with architectures $\mathcal{V}_1, \mathcal{V}_2, \mathcal{V}_3$) on the *training* representations to predict U , and evaluate its AUC on the *test* set to obtain the adversary AUC and extraction score.
- We compute DEO on the *test* set for the classifier trained with each (Z_i, \mathcal{V}_j) configuration.

What we vary. We sweep representation layer Z_i and discriminator depth \mathcal{V}_j to produce the plots in Figure 1a (adversary AUC) and Figure 1b (DEO). Test data is used for evaluation.

Key observations. (i) External adversaries with greater capacity recover more sensitive information from deeper layers when the training discriminator is weaker; (ii) regularizing the penultimate layer with a sufficiently expressive discriminator (penultimate + 3-layer discriminator) yields the lowest DEO on the test set; (iii) regularizing layers near to the output yields better performance in general.

Remark 7 (The Ideal Discriminator Complexity). Empirical results on the Health dataset bridge the gap between our theoretical bounds:

- **Fragility of the Canonical:** While training AUC is near zero (the penultimate Z is optimized to fool the 1-layer training

Fig. 2: Accuracy vs DEO on the test set. Each curve is produced by varying λ and selecting discriminator complexity via validation. Our method outperforms Adversarial Debiasing (AD) on Credit and Health.

discriminator), test AUC spikes significantly. This confirms **Prop. 2**, showing that optimal canonical discriminators are fragile to the distribution shifts, which also are analogous to the shift from train to test sets (**Prop. 1**).

- **Over-Robustness of MI:** Conversely, **Prop. 3** suggests MI based discriminators (i.e. unbounded complexity) are robust to any shift within the support, no matter how extreme.
- **The key takeaway:** Our results suggest the ideal discriminator lies between these two extremes. We find that a **3-layer discriminator** at the **penultimate layer** provides the best trade-off, outperforming the 1-layer canonical discriminator by being robust enough to generalize, without the computational or theoretical over-robustness of MI.

C. Accuracy–Fairness tradeoffs (varying λ)

Goal. Produce accuracy–fairness curves by varying the fairness regularization weight λ , selecting the best discriminator complexity via validation, and comparing this approach to the adversarial debiasing baseline.

Protocol. For each dataset and each λ in a predefined grid:

- 1) For each discriminator family \mathcal{V}_j and representation layer candidate Z_i , train on the training set and evaluate DEO on the validation set.
- 2) Select the (Z_i, \mathcal{V}_j) configuration that minimizes validation DEO (ties broken by validation accuracy).
- 3) Retrain the selected configuration on the combined train+validation split (same hyperparameter settings) and report final accuracy and DEO on the test set.

We apply the same selection procedure to the adversarial debiasing baseline to ensure a fair comparison.

Results (summary). Figure 2 shows accuracy vs DEO curves on all three datasets. Across datasets, our procedure (validation-selected discriminator complexity and layer) yields strictly better or competitive DEO for the same accuracy compared to Adversarial Debiasing (AD) [9] and FCRL [10]. In particular, on the Credit and Health datasets we observe a clear improvement in accuracy at fixed DEO levels.

Key observations. Evaluating all metrics on held-out test sets, we find that (i) adversary capacity and representation layer critically determine how much sensitive information can be extracted, and (ii) tuning discriminator complexity via

validation yields better accuracy–fairness tradeoffs than a one-size-fits-all adversarial debiasing baseline.

Remark 8 (Overall Implications). These results further confirm that the canonical 1-layer discriminator is a sub-optimal default. The results are better in all three datasets except in Adult where the best tradeoff is achieved by adversarial de-biasing. However, in Adult we also see adversarial debiasing suffer significantly for larger values of lambda which is avoided by our approach. The fact that our (Z_i, \mathcal{V}_j) selection consistently yields better accuracy–fairness curves overall compared to standard adversarial debiasing validates our theory: the ideal discriminator must be complex enough to escape the **fragility** of Prop. 2 but restricted enough to avoid the **over-robustness** of Prop. 3.

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APPENDIX
PROOFS OF THEORETICAL RESULTS

Before we outline the proofs, we summarize some details that were not reported in the main paper:

Proposition 1. (Generalization as Robustness to Distribution Shifts; from Theorem 2 in [6]) Let P be a probability law on \mathbb{R}^d with $d > 2$, and let $\hat{P}_m = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \delta_{X_i}$ be the empirical law of m i.i.d. samples from P . Denote by $W_1(\cdot, \cdot)$ the 1-Wasserstein distance. Assume P has an exponential moment of order 2, i.e., there exists a $\gamma > 0$ such that $\mathcal{E}_{2,\gamma}(P) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} e^{\gamma|x|^2} P(dx) < \infty$.

Then there exist positive constants $C, c > 0$ (depending only on $p = 1$, d , and on $2, \gamma, \mathcal{E}_{2,\gamma}(P)$) such that the following holds: for any confidence level $\delta \in (0, 1)$,

$$r_{m,\delta} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\log(C/\delta)}{cm}\right)^{1/d}, & \delta \geq C e^{-cm}, \\ \left(\frac{\log(C/\delta)}{cm}\right)^{1/2}, & \delta < C e^{-cm}, \end{cases}$$

and, with probability at least $1 - \delta$,

$$|\mathbb{E}_{\hat{P}_m}[f] - \mathbb{E}_P[f]| \leq \sup_{Q: W_1(Q, \hat{P}_m) \leq r_{m,\delta}} |\mathbb{E}_Q[f] - \mathbb{E}_{\hat{P}_m}[f]|$$

for any statistic f . Note that the positive constants C and c depend only on $p = 1$, the dimension d , and on the exponential moment parameters $(\gamma, \mathcal{E}_{2,\gamma}(P))$.

Proof. Set $p = 1$ and assume P satisfies the exponential moment condition $\mathcal{E}_{2,\gamma}(P) < \infty$. Then we are in case (1) of Theorem 2 of [6] with $\alpha = 2 > p = 1$. Hence there exist constants $C, c > 0$ depending only on $(d, p, \gamma, \mathcal{E}_{2,\gamma}(P))$ such that for all $m \geq 1$ and all $x > 0$,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(W_1(\hat{P}_m, P) \geq x\right) \leq \begin{cases} C \exp(-cmx^d), & 0 < x \leq 1, \\ C \exp(-cmx^2), & x > 1. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Fix $\delta \in (0, 1)$. To obtain a radius $r_{m,\delta}$ such that $\mathbb{P}(W_1(\hat{P}_m, P) \leq r_{m,\delta}) \geq 1 - \delta$, invert the two branches of (1).

If $\delta \geq C e^{-cm}$, then the solution of $C e^{-cmr^d} = \delta$ satisfies $r \leq 1$, giving

$$r_{m,\delta} = \left(\frac{\log(C/\delta)}{cm}\right)^{1/d}.$$

If $\delta < C e^{-cm}$, then the solution of $C e^{-cmr^2} = \delta$ satisfies $r > 1$, giving

$$r_{m,\delta} = \left(\frac{\log(C/\delta)}{cm}\right)^{1/2}.$$

Thus $W_1(\hat{P}_m, P) \leq r_{m,\delta}$ with probability at least $1 - \delta$.

Finally, the event the true distribution P lies in the Wasserstein ball is $\{Q : W_1(Q, \hat{P}_m) \leq r_{m,\delta}\}$. So for any measurable f with probability at least $1 - \delta$,

$$|\mathbb{E}_{\hat{P}_m}[f] - \mathbb{E}_P[f]| \leq \sup_{Q: W_1(Q, \hat{P}_m) \leq r_{m,\delta}} |\mathbb{E}_Q[f] - \mathbb{E}_{\hat{P}_m}[f]|.$$

This proves the proposition. □

Theorem 1 (Necessity and Sufficiency). Let F be a classifier with features Z . F is guaranteed to satisfy the Equalized Odds criterion if and only if for every label $y \in \{0, 1\}$, the optimal discriminator in \mathcal{D}_{EO} fails to reduce the cross-entropy loss \mathcal{L} below the entropy of the sensitive attribute:

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{D}_{EO}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] = H(U \mid Y = y) \quad (6)$$

Proof. Fix any label $y \in \{0, 1\}$ and condition on $Y = y$ throughout. Let $U \in \{0, 1\}$ be the sensitive attribute, and write

$$p := \Pr(U = 0 \mid Y = y), \quad 1 - p := \Pr(U = 1 \mid Y = y).$$

The classifier F is a sigmoid binary classifier with logit $g_\theta(Z)$ and prediction

$$\hat{Y} = \mathbb{1}\{g_\theta(Z) > 0\}.$$

The canonical discriminator class \mathcal{D}_{EO} consists of functions

$$h(Z) = a + b \cdot \sigma_H(g_\theta(Z)),$$

with σ_H the hard-sigmoid. Under the constraints $0 \leq a, a + b \leq 1$ and $2a + b = 1$, we have $a + b = 1 - a$, so

$$h(Z) = \begin{cases} a, & g_\theta(Z) \leq 0, \\ 1 - a, & g_\theta(Z) > 0. \end{cases}$$

We denote $I := \mathbb{1}\{g_\theta(Z) > 0\}$ and $q := \Pr(I = 1 \mid Y = y)$.

The cross-entropy loss of h for predicting U given Z (conditioned on $Y = y$) is

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] = -\mathbb{E}[U \log h(Z) + (1 - U) \log(1 - h(Z)) \mid Y = y].$$

We decompose this over the two regions $I = 1$ and $I = 0$:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] = q \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid I = 1, Y = y] + (1 - q) \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid I = 0, Y = y].$$

On $I = 1$ we have $h(Z) = 1 - a$, so

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid I = 1, Y = y] = -\left(\Pr(U = 1 \mid I = 1, Y = y) \log(1 - a) + \Pr(U = 0 \mid I = 1, Y = y) \log a \right).$$

On $I = 0$ we have $h(Z) = a$, so

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid I = 0, Y = y] = -\left(\Pr(U = 1 \mid I = 0, Y = y) \log a + \Pr(U = 0 \mid I = 0, Y = y) \log(1 - a) \right).$$

We now prove necessity and sufficiency.

(Necessity). Assume F satisfies Equalized Odds for label y , i.e.

$$\Pr(\widehat{Y} = 1 \mid U = 0, Y = y) = \Pr(\widehat{Y} = 1 \mid U = 1, Y = y).$$

Since $\widehat{Y} = 1$ iff $I = 1$, this is

$$\Pr(I = 1 \mid U = 0, Y = y) = \Pr(I = 1 \mid U = 1, Y = y) =: r.$$

By Bayes' rule,

$$\Pr(U = 0 \mid I = 1, Y = y) = \frac{\Pr(I = 1 \mid U = 0, Y = y) \Pr(U = 0 \mid Y = y)}{\Pr(I = 1 \mid Y = y)}.$$

But

$$\Pr(I = 1 \mid Y = y) = \sum_{u \in \{0,1\}} \Pr(I = 1 \mid U = u, Y = y) \Pr(U = u \mid Y = y) = r (\Pr(U = 0 \mid Y = y) + \Pr(U = 1 \mid Y = y)) = r.$$

Hence

$$\Pr(U = 0 \mid I = 1, Y = y) = \Pr(U = 0 \mid Y = y) = p,$$

and similarly $\Pr(U = 1 \mid I = 1, Y = y) = 1 - p$. An analogous argument for $I = 0$ yields

$$\Pr(U = u \mid I = i, Y = y) = \Pr(U = u \mid Y = y), \quad \forall u \in \{0,1\}, i \in \{0,1\}.$$

Thus

$$U \perp I \mid Y = y.$$

Substituting these equalities into the loss expressions, we get

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid I = 1, Y = y] = -((1 - p) \log(1 - a) + p \log a),$$

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid I = 0, Y = y] = -((1 - p) \log a + p \log(1 - a)).$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] = q \ell_1(a) + (1 - q) \ell_0(a),$$

where

$$\ell_1(a) = -((1 - p) \log(1 - a) + p \log a), \quad \ell_0(a) = -((1 - p) \log a + p \log(1 - a)).$$

We see that the discriminator loss is minimized only when $a = p$, achieving the final cross-entropy loss as

$$H(U \mid Y = y) = -(p \log p + (1 - p) \log(1 - p)).$$

Since $U \perp I \mid Y = y$, the indicator I carries no information about U beyond Y , and any function of I (in particular, any $h \in \mathcal{D}_{EO}$) cannot reduce the loss below $H(U \mid Y = y)$. Hence

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{D}_{EO}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] = H(U \mid Y = y).$$

(Sufficiency).

Fix y and condition on $Y = y$. Assume F does *not* satisfy EO, so there exists a group for which

$$\Pr(\widehat{Y} = y \mid U = 0, Y = y) \neq \Pr(\widehat{Y} = y \mid U = 1, Y = y).$$

Since $\widehat{Y} = 1$ iff $g(Z) > 0$, the same inequality holds with $g(Z) > 0$ in place of $\widehat{Y} = y$. Repeating the Bayes-rule manipulation from the necessity part now yields

$$\Pr(U = 0 \mid g(Z) > 0, Y = y) > \Pr(U = 0 \mid Y = y) =: p,$$

and therefore also $\Pr(U = 0 \mid g(Z) \leq 0, Y = y) < p$ by the law of total probability. Thus the two regions $g(Z) > 0$ and $g(Z) \leq 0$ have strictly different class proportions.

For the canonical discriminator, $h(Z) = 1 - a$ on $g(Z) > 0$ and $h(Z) = a$ on $g(Z) \leq 0$. Its cross-entropy loss decomposes as before:

$$q \ell_1(a) + (1 - q) \ell_0(a),$$

where $\ell_1(a)$ and $\ell_0(a)$ are the Bernoulli cross-entropies with parameters $p_1 = \Pr(U = 0 \mid g(Z) > 0, Y = y)$ and $p_0 = \Pr(U = 0 \mid g(Z) \leq 0, Y = y)$ respectively. Since $p_1 > p > p_0$ and binary entropy is strictly concave, choosing a so that h moves toward p_1 on $g(Z) > 0$ and toward p_0 on $g(Z) \leq 0$ yields

$$q \ell_1(a) + (1 - q) \ell_0(a) < -(p \log p + (1 - p) \log(1 - p)) = H(U \mid Y = y).$$

Hence the discriminator achieves strictly smaller loss than $H(U \mid Y = y)$ whenever EO is violated. The contrapositive gives the desired sufficiency.

This proves the result. \square

Proposition 2 (Fragility under Distribution Shift). *Consider a Canonical Discriminator \mathcal{D}_{EO} under a distribution $P(Z)$, and any shifted distribution $Q(Z)$ satisfying $\text{TV}(P, Q) = \delta > 0$ with $\text{supp}(Q) \subseteq \text{supp}(P)$. Then for every $y \in \{0, 1\}$ and for $\delta \rightarrow 0$, the optimal discriminator in \mathcal{D}_{EO} under Q satisfies*

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{D}_{EO}} \mathbb{E}_Q[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) \mid Y = y] \geq H(U \mid Y = y) - \max\left\{\frac{\delta^2}{2 \ln 2}, \left|\ln \frac{p}{1 - p}\right| \frac{\delta}{2 \ln 2}\right\},$$

where $p = P(U = 1 \mid Y = y)$.

Remark 9. *Please note that the original proposition statement only assumed the case when $P(U = 1 \mid Y = y) = P(U = 0 \mid Y = y) = 0.5$ (i.e., $p = 0.5$). The refined result distinguishes the cases $p = \frac{1}{2}$ and $p \neq \frac{1}{2}$: when $p \neq \frac{1}{2}$, the first-order Taylor expansion term dominates, yielding a linear dependence on δ , while the quadratic bound applies only in the case $p = \frac{1}{2}$. This is a stronger result that highlights more significant reduction in discriminator loss than the original.*

Proof. Let $Y = y$ be fixed. Under the fair distribution P , Equalized Odds implies $U \perp S$. Let $p = P(U = 1)$ and $\alpha = P(S = 1)$.

The Canonical Discriminator h outputs a for $S = 1$ and $1 - a$ for $S = 0$. Given a shifted distribution Q , the expected loss is:

$$\mathbb{E}_Q[\mathcal{L}] = -M_Q \ln a - (1 - M_Q) \ln(1 - a)$$

where $M_Q = Q(U = 1, S = 1) + Q(U = 0, S = 0)$ is the total matching mass. Setting the derivative $\frac{\partial \mathbb{E}}{\partial a} = 0$ yields the optimal output $a^* = M_Q$. The minimized loss is the binary entropy:

$$\min_a \mathbb{E}_Q[\mathcal{L}] = H(M_Q)$$

As $\text{TV}(P, Q) = \delta$, if we assume that ϵ mass is shifted in M_Q , we will have:

$$M_Q = \underbrace{p\alpha + (1-p)(1-\alpha)}_{a_0} + \epsilon$$

where a_0 is the match probability under P .

The ϵ that maximizes the reduction of entropy will be the largest possible value it can take as well. To derive that, we first assume the case when $\delta = 0$, as then $M_Q = M_P$ simply. We write $M_P = P(U=1, S=1) + P(U=0, S=0)$ and under Q set $M_Q = M_P + \epsilon$. Then $R_Q = 1 - M_Q = R_P - \epsilon$, and since $\text{TV}(P, Q) = \sum_{u,s} |Q_{us} - P_{us}| = \delta$, we have $2|\epsilon| \leq \delta$, hence $|\epsilon| \leq \delta/2$.

Under EO, $U \perp S$, so $M_P = p\alpha + (1-p)(1-\alpha) \in [1-p, p]$. Assume $p \geq 1/2$ without loss of generality; to minimize $H(M_Q)$ we first must maximize M_P , thus we can simply set $M_P = p$. Thus $M_Q = p + \epsilon$ with $0 \leq \epsilon \leq \delta/2$. Thus we can just set $\epsilon = \delta/2$

Using the binary entropy $H_2(x)$ and its derivatives $H_2'(x) = \ln \frac{1-x}{x} \frac{1}{\ln 2}$ and $H_2''(x) = -1/(x(1-x) \ln 2)$, a second-order Taylor expansion gives

$$H_2(p + \delta/2) = H_2(p) - \left(\ln \frac{p}{1-p} \right) \frac{\delta}{2 \ln 2} - \frac{\delta^2}{8p(1-p) \ln 2} + o(\delta^3) + \dots$$

If $p = 1/2$ then $H_2'(p) = 0$ and the second order term is the largest term active in the expansion, yielding the final result:

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{D}_{EO}} \mathbb{E}_Q[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) | Y = y] \geq H(U | Y = y) - \frac{\delta^2}{2 \ln 2}.$$

If $p \neq 1/2$, the linear term is negative, so it provides the natural lower bound as the higher order terms are negligible compared to it:

$$\min_{h \in \mathcal{D}_{EO}} \mathbb{E}_Q[\mathcal{L}(h(Z), U) | Y = y] \geq H(U | Y = y) - \left| \ln \left(\frac{p}{1-p} \right) \right| \frac{\delta}{2 \ln 2}.$$

This completes the proof. □

Proposition 3 (Robustness of Information-Theoretic Fairness). *Let P be a source distribution over (Z, U, Y) such that $I_P(Z; U | Y) = 0$. Let Q be any target distribution obtained by changing only the marginal over Z (i.e. $Q(Z) = Q_Z$, keeping other conditionals over Z intact). Then the representation remains perfectly fair under $Q: I_Q(Z; U | Y) = 0$, and, for any measurable classifier head $g: \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$, Equality of Odds is preserved,*

$$Q(g(Z) | U = 0, Y = y) = Q(g(Z) | U = 1, Y = y) \quad \text{for all } y \in \{0, 1\}.$$

Remark 10. *We noted that the nature of the distributions P and Q could be made clearer, so the above statement has been slightly updated. The robustness result relies on the fact that only the marginal distribution over Z is altered when passing from P to Q , while all conditionals $P(U, Y | Z)$ remain fixed. This corresponds to changing the sampling of representations without modifying the underlying causal or conditional structure. Under this restriction, conditional independence $Z \perp U | Y$ is preserved, and thus Equality of Odds continues to hold for any classifier head.*

Proof. From $I_P(Z; U | Y) = 0$ we have $Z \perp U | Y$ under P , i.e.

$$P(u, z | y) = P(u | y) P(z | y) \quad \text{for all } (u, z, y) \text{ in the support of } P.$$

Equivalently,

$$P(u | z, y) = P(u | y) \quad \text{for all } z \in \text{supp}(P_Z | Y = y).$$

By construction,

$$Q(z, u, y) = Q_Z(z) P(u, y | z) = Q_Z(z) P(y | z) P(u | y, z).$$

Using $P(u | y, z) = P(u | y)$, we get

$$Q(z, u, y) = Q_Z(z) P(y | z) P(u | y).$$

Thus, for any y with $Q(Y = y) > 0$,

$$Q(z, u | y) = \frac{Q(z, u, y)}{Q(y)} = P(u | y) \frac{Q_Z(z) P(y | z)}{Q(y)} = P(u | y) Q(z | y),$$

so $Z \perp U | Y$ under Q , hence $I_Q(Z; U | Y) = 0$.

Finally, for any measurable g and any y ,

$$Q(g(Z) = \hat{y}, U = u | Y = y) = \sum_{z: g(z) = \hat{y}} Q(z, u | y) = P(u | y) \sum_{z: g(z) = \hat{y}} Q(z | y),$$

so

$$Q(g(Z) = \hat{y} | U = u, Y = y) = \frac{P(u | y) \sum_{z: g(z) = \hat{y}} Q(z | y)}{P(u | y)} = \sum_{z: g(z) = \hat{y}} Q(z | y),$$

which does not depend on u . Hence

$$Q(g(Z) | U = 0, Y = y) = Q(g(Z) | U = 1, Y = y),$$

i.e. Equality of Odds holds under Q . □

Theorem 2 (Fragility of Non-Zero Mutual Information). *Let Z be a representation such that $I(Z; U | Y) > 0$, and let the classifier head be a linear function. If the conditional entropy $H(U | Z, Y)$ is L -Lipschitz, then there exists a distribution Q and a classifier F with $\text{supp}(Q) \subseteq \text{supp}(P)$ such that F violates equalized odds on Q .*

Proof. Fix y and write $p_1(z) = P(U = 1 | Z = z, Y = y)$, $p_0(z) = 1 - p_1(z)$, and $p = P(U = 1 | Y = y)$, $1 - p = P(U = 0 | Y = y)$. The condition $I(Z; U | Y) > 0$ implies $H(U | Z, Y = y) < H(U | Y = y)$, so there is a set of z of positive measure with $H(U | Z = z, Y = y) < H(U | Y = y)$.

Define the likelihood ratio $r(z) = \frac{p_1(z)/p}{p_0(z)/(1-p)}$. If $r(z) \equiv 1$ almost surely, then U and Z would be independent given $Y = y$, contradicting $I(Z; U | Y) > 0$. Hence there exist z_1, z_2 such that $r(z_1) > 1$ and $r(z_2) < 1$. Equivalently,

$$\frac{P(U = 1 | z_1, y)}{P(U = 1 | y)} > \frac{P(U = 0 | z_1, y)}{P(U = 0 | y)}, \quad \frac{P(U = 1 | z_2, y)}{P(U = 1 | y)} < \frac{P(U = 0 | z_2, y)}{P(U = 0 | y)}.$$

Let $h(z) = H(U | Z = z, Y = y)$. Since h is L -Lipschitz and $h(z_i) < H(U | Y = y)$, there exist radii $\rho_i = (H(U | Y = y) - h(z_i))/L > 0$ such that for all z with $\|z - z_i\| \leq \rho_i$ we have $h(z) \leq H(U | Y = y)$. By continuity of $p_1(z)$ in z , the sign of $r(z) - 1$ cannot flip inside a sufficiently small ball around each z_i , so shrinking ρ_i if necessary we may assume $r(z) > 1$ for all z in $B_1 := \{z : \|z - z_1\| \leq \rho_1\}$ and $r(z) < 1$ for all z in $B_2 := \{z : \|z - z_2\| \leq \rho_2\}$.

Define Q by restricting P to $B_1 \cup B_2$ and renormalizing (so $\text{supp}(Q) \subseteq \text{supp}(P)$). Under $Q(\cdot | Y = y)$, points in B_1 are relatively enriched in $U = 1$ compared to the prior $P(U | Y = y)$, while points in B_2 are relatively enriched in $U = 0$.

Since the head is linear, choose a linear classifier $F(z) = \mathbf{1}\{w^\top z > t\}$ that separates B_1 and B_2 (e.g. w pointing from the center of B_2 to B_1 and t between their projections). Then $F(Z) = 1$ occurs predominantly on B_1 and $F(Z) = 0$ on B_2 . Because U has different conditional biases on B_1 and B_2 , we obtain

$$Q(F(Z) = 1 | U = 1, Y = y) \neq Q(F(Z) = 1 | U = 0, Y = y),$$

so Equalized Odds is violated under Q . □